

THEORETICAL TUTORIAL OF SUPERVISED CAUSALITY APPROACH IN CONCEPTUAL COGNITIVE MODELING

Iman Ghodratiostani^{1,2}

¹Neurocognitive Engineering Laboratory (NEL), Center for Engineering Applied to Health, Institute of Mathematics and Computer Science, University of Sao Paulo, Brazil;

²Institute of Mathematics and Computer Science, University of São Paulo, São Carlos, Brazil;

Correspondence*:
Iman Ghodratiostani
iman.ghodrati@usp.br

2 ABSTRACT

This technical report aims to provide the simplified theoretical knowledge needed to interpret and develop new mediatory models by non-experts in statistical modeling relying on their cognitive problems. Multi-mediatory models are employed to reveal the causality relationship between the cognitive conceptual model compartments, which must be supported with rational evidence. The inferential mediatory models can be developed in either IBM-SPSS, SAS, or R platform.

Keywords: Conceptual Cognitive Model, Causality Model, Mediatory Model, and Predictive Model

1 BACKGROUND

A linear regression model represents an equation that links features (input) to a target variable (output) by a linear relationship. Linear regression analysis intends to estimate the regression model's various parameters to estimate the target variable with independent variables reasonably. The result of a regression model can test hypotheses about the processes that link predictors and targets.

2 SIMPLE LINEAR REGRESSION MODEL

A simple linear regression model contains only a single predictor variable.

$$Y_j = \beta_0 + \beta X_j + \varepsilon_j \quad (1)$$

Y_j and X_j refer to the case j 's measurement and a target and predictor variable, respectively, β is the regression coefficient for the predictor variable, β_0 is the intercept or regression constant, and ε_j is the error of regression or residual. Suppose β_0 , and β is identified so we can generate an estimate of Y from X with a variant of this model:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{Y}_j &= \hat{\beta}_0 + \hat{\beta} X_j \\ Y_j &= \hat{Y}_j + \hat{\varepsilon}_j \\ \hat{\varepsilon}_j &= Y_j - \hat{Y}_j \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

14 The optimum estimation will achieve when ()data is minimized.

$$OLS = SS_{\text{residual}} = \sum_{j=1}^n (Y_j - \hat{Y}_j)^2 = \sum_{j=1}^n \hat{\varepsilon}_j^2 \quad (3)$$

15 and the total sum of squares defines as

$$SS_{\text{total}} = \sum_{j=1}^n (Y_j - \bar{Y})^2 \quad (4)$$

The simple linear regression model expresses a mathematical relationship between X to Y with a line equation. The regression coefficient corresponds to the line's slope and b_0 to intercept in the linear regression equation. Multiple Linear Regression The multiple linear regression model estimates a target variable using more than one predictor variable. In its most general form, a multiple linear regression model with k features variables takes the form

$$Y_j = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{1j} + \beta_2 x_{2j} + \dots + \beta_k x_{kj} + \varepsilon_j \quad (5)$$

and in matrix notation is:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Y} &= \mathbf{x}'\beta + \varepsilon \quad \text{where } \mathbf{x}' = \{1, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k\}' \\ \hat{\mathbf{Y}} &= \mathbf{x}'\hat{\beta} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

16 2.1 Model Fit Measurements

17 The multiple regression equation minimizes the Mean Square residuals (MS_{residual}), consequently
18 obtaining the best linear fitting model.

$$MS_{\text{residual}} = \frac{SS_{\text{residual}}}{n - k - 1} \quad (7)$$

19 where n is the number of observations and k is the number of features, generally $(n-k-1)$ is also called
20 degrees of freedom. An alternative measure of fit is the standard error of estimate and defined as

$$\text{Standard error of estimate} = \sqrt{MS_{\text{residual}}} = \sqrt{\frac{SS_{\text{residual}}}{n - k - 1}} \quad (8)$$

21 Multiple Correlation Coefficient (R) and R^2 represent the proportion of the variance in Y explained by the
22 model and formulated as

$$R^2 = \frac{SS_{\text{total}} - SS_{\text{residual}}}{SS_{\text{total}}} \quad (9)$$

23
24

25 2.2 Assumptions for Interpretation and Statistical Inference

26 1. Linearity

27 regression assumes that all features x are individually related with the target variable Y linearly.

28 Whenever the essential linearity assumption is violated, the regression coefficient's interpretation is
29 meaningless Darlington and Hayes (2016).

30 2. Normality

31 The normality assumption asserts that the errors in estimating target variable Y , conditioned on x ,
32 are typically distributed. Simulation studies identified that only severe violations of the normality
33 assumption considerably affect the validity of statistical inferences from a regression analysis unless
34 the sample size is relatively small Duncan and Layard (1973); Edgell and Noon (1984); Havlicek
35 and Peterson (1977); Hayes (1996). However, non-normality can affect sampling variance in some
36 situations, reducing hypothesis tests' power and the certainty of rejecting the insignificant null
37 hypothesis.

38 3. Homoscedasticity

39 The assumption of homoscedasticity states that the errors in the estimation of Y are equally variable
40 conditioned on x . When it fails to detect, heteroscedasticity happens, affecting both the validity
41 of inference and reducing hypothesis tests' statistical power. Therefore, influence the precision of
42 confidence intervals for regression coefficients. An informal test of homoscedasticity is a visual
43 inspection of the residuals' scatterplot as a function of $\hat{\epsilon}$.

44 4. Independence of observations

45 OLS regression assumes the errors in estimation are statistically independent. The errors in estimation
46 are independent when there is no information available in the error of estimation of Y_i that could
47 estimate the error of Y_j .

48 5. Non-multicollinearity between the Features

49 Multicollinearity refers to a situation in which more than two features in a multiple regression model
50 are extremely linearly related.

51 3 MEDIATOR

52 An investigator to discover how X affects Y generally hypothesizes that mediating variables M can influence
53 the relation between X and Y (Mediator models depicted in Figures (1, 2, and 3) Hayes (2017). Therefore,
54 investigators are interested in measuring X 's direct effect on Y , besides mediatory analyses and identifying
55 causal relationships. MacKinnon et al. (2002); Preacher and Hayes (2004, 2008); Baron and Kenny (1986).

56 3.1 simple Mediator

57 Mediation analysis evaluates evidence from studies designed to test hypotheses about how features X
58 causally transmit effects on a target variable Y . A simple mediation model contains two target variables
59 (M) and (Y) and two features (X) and (M) whereas X causally affecting Y and M , and M causally
60 affecting Y . A simple mediator model is a causal system that one causal feature X leads to an outcome Y
61 through a single intermediary variable M . in other words, X from two unidirectional pathways can affect
62 Y .

- 63 • One leads from X to Y directly and is called the direct effect of X on Y .
- 64 • The second from X to Y is the indirect influence of X on Y over M .

Figure 1. Simple Mediator diagram, X, M, and Y represents Predictor, Mediator and Target variable, respectively.

Estimation of the Direct, Indirect, and Total Effects of X As there are two target variables in the simple mediator diagram (Figure 1), two linear models are needed, one for each target.

$$M = \beta_{0M} + aX + \varepsilon_M \tag{10}$$

$$Y = \beta_{0Y} + c'X + bM + \varepsilon_Y \tag{11}$$

$$Y = \beta_{0Y} + c'X + b(\beta_{0M} + aX + \varepsilon_M) + \varepsilon_Y$$

$$Y = (\beta_{0Y} + b\beta_{0M}) + (ab + c')X + (\varepsilon_Y + b\varepsilon_M)$$

$$c = c' + ab \tag{12}$$

$$Y = \beta_{0Y*} + cX + \varepsilon_{Y*} \tag{13}$$

65 where β_{0M} and β_{0Y} are regression constants, ε_M and ε_Y are error in estimation of M and Y , respectively.
 66 a , b , and c' are the regression coefficients given to the features in the regression models to estimate target
 67 variables. c' estimates the direct effect of X on Y and a quantifies the effect of X on M , and c' represents
 68 the direct effect of M on Y . In the Equation(13), $c' + ab$ replaced with c . Errors of estimations and
 69 intercepts also integrated with Y^* for simplifications.

70 It is essential to consider this mathematics, whereby c applies when Y and M are estimated using regression,
 71 meaning they are analyzed as continuous variables using the OLS criterion for maximizing the fit of the
 72 model. It also works when using a maximum-likelihood-based model of continuous outcomes, but it does
 73 not applicable for using other modeling methods like generalized linear modeling.

74 **Statistical inference**

75 Bootstrap Confidence Interval is a resampling method that needs high-speed computing, so as
 76 computer power has increased, the bootstrapping approach is implemented in modern statistical software.
 77 Bootstrapping is helpful when the behavior of a statistic over repeated sampling is either not known or
 78 highly depends on context. The original sample of size n is treated as a small representation of the sampled
 79 population. Observations in this sample are then "resampled" with replacement, and some statistic of
 80 interest was calculated in the new sample of size n created by this resampling method.

81 In mediation analysis, bootstrapping is employed to represent the indirect effect's sampling distribution
 82 empirically. This empirical representation is utilized to build a confidence interval for the null hypotheses
 83 that respect the irregularity of the sampling distribution of ab and yield accurate inferences.

84 **3.2 Parallel Multi-Mediator**

In parallel multiple mediator models, Predictor X affects target Y directly and indirectly through two or more mediators, with the condition that no mediator causally affects another. The statistical diagram of a parallel multi-mediator model with k isolated mediators that have no effects on each other (presented in Figure 2).

It does not mean mediators are independent. However, parallel multi-mediator, in comparison to multiple

Figure 2. Parallel Multi-Mediator diagram, parallel mediators $\{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_k\}$ assumed has no influence on each others.

single mediator models, could boost power for tests of indirect effects if the mediators are highly correlated with Y but weakly correlated with each other. It also makes it possible to compare the sizes of the indirect effects through different mediators. As can be seen in Figure 2, a parallel multiple mediator models with k mediators has $k + 1$ target variables and so requires $k + 1$ equations to estimate all the causal effects of X on Y . These equations are

$$M_i = \beta_{0M_i} + a_i X + \varepsilon_{M_i} \quad \text{for all } i=1 \text{ to } k \tag{14}$$

$$Y = \beta_{0Y} + c' X + \sum_{i=1}^k b_i M_i + \varepsilon_Y \tag{15}$$

$$c = c' + \sum_{i=1}^k a_i b_i \tag{16}$$

85 where a_i measures the effect of X on M_i , b_i calculates the effect of M_i on Y examining for X and the other
 86 $(k - 1)M$ variables. c' also assesses the effect of X on Y , holding all M mediator variables as constant.
 87 Furthermore, in Equation(16), c is the total effect of X .

88

Figure 3. Serial Multi-Mediator diagram demonstrated for two mediators for restriction in visualizations

89 **3.3 Serial Multi-Mediator**

90 The serial multi-mediator model assumes no causal association between two or more mediators. The
 91 direct, indirect, and total effects of X on Y are investigated when consecutively hypothesized X causes
 92 M_1 , then M_1 leads M_2 , and so forth, achieving Y as the final target.

$$M_1 = \beta_{0M_1} + a_1X + \varepsilon_{M_1}$$

$$M_i = \beta_{0M_i} + a_iX + \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} d_{ij}M_j + \varepsilon_{M_j} \quad \text{for all } i = 2 \text{ to } k \quad (17)$$

$$Y = \beta_{0Y} + c'X + \sum_{i=1}^k b_iM_i + \varepsilon_Y \quad (18)$$

93 By integrating all introduced models here, we are able to make any diagram of complex unidirectional
 94 mediator models.
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